

Laboratory-scale analysis of road-deposited sediment wash-off: Runoff scenarios under high sediment loads

C.A. Zafra^{1,*}, D.S. Hernández¹, J. Suárez², J. Naves² and J. Anta²

¹Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería Ambiental—GIIAUD, Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas, Bogotá E-111711, Colombia

²Grupo de Ingeniería del Agua y del Medio Ambiente—GEAMA, Universidade da Coruña, Spain

*Corresponding author email: czafra@udistrital.edu.co

Highlights

- Direct relationship between the rain intensity and remaining RDS load (gully pot/manhole).
- Increasing rain intensity increases the concentration peak into the manhole.
- The concentration peak occurs faster when the rain intensity increases.

Introduction

The washing of road-deposited sediments (RDSs) from surface runoff is a common problem in urban areas and can have several negative impacts on the environment, infrastructure and people's quality of life (Yarmoshenko et al., 2020). Total suspended solids (TSS) concentrations are often used as indicators in the study of RDS transport by runoff (Wang et al., 2018). Thus, physical modelling of laboratory-scale TSS washing is an important tool for optimizing existing management and treatment techniques to minimize the impact of RDSs and associated pollutants (Venghaus et al., 2023). Forecasting RDS washing load using rainfall-runoff modelling systems plays a significant role in the development of urban drainage systems (Hu and Zhao, 2022). Accurate modelling of RDS washing is important for making decisions based on sediment transport and water quality. However, RDS washing modelling is not a straightforward exercise, as it often involves empirically calibrated equations that contain parameters of a highly variable nature such as rainfall (duration and intensity), catchment surface (roughness, slope and drainage system components) and particle characteristics (sediment load and granulometry) (García-Haba et al., 2023). The RDS washing is the phenomenon by which sediment is removed from the road surface by the action of rainfall and runoff. There are two main processes involved in the RDS washing from an impervious surface. These processes are the RDS accumulation in dry weather and the RDS removal by the action of rainfall and runoff (L. Li et al., 2023). There are several types of laboratory models that are used to simulate RDS washing from road surfaces. In the context of this study, there is particular interest in the joint use of rainfall simulators and rainfall-runoff channels (D. Li et al., 2023) under urban road drainage conditions and high RDS loads.

The main objective of this paper is to analyse by means of a physical laboratory model the RDS washing under different rainfall/runoff scenarios and high sediment loads. The physical model considers consecutively the following components: road surface, gully pot and manhole. This study is relevant due to the following practical aspects. (1) To study the influences of rainfall intensity and RDS load on the washing phenomenon in a road drainage system (remaining load and particle size distribution). (2) To analyse the behaviour of water quality indicator parameters in a road drainage system. (3) To evaluate the possible implications in the design and selection of road drainage systems.

Methodology

Physical model description

The physical model at laboratory scale consisted of a rainfall simulator and a runoff channel. The rainfall simulator allowed intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h to be considered. Rainfall was distributed by means of a pressurized drippers system, which also integrated a metallic mesh for uniform distribution over the study sub-basin (Figure 1). The runoff channel of the physical model had nine sub catchments, five of which were street type (B1, B2, B3, B4 and B5) and four of roof type (B6, B7, B8 and B9). The longitudinal slope of the model was 1% and transverse slope was 2%. The surface was impermeable (concrete). The physical model had four manholes (N2, N3, N5 and N6) that received the runoff generated and an outlet pipe (O1), whose

conduction direction begins at N1-N2-N3-N5-N6-O1. Alternatively, N4 had the same conduction direction; however, it was only connected to three manholes (N5-N6-O1). In this study, gully pot 2 and manhole covers N2 and N3 were sealed to create a single basin with sub-basins B1 and B2 draining all runoff to the gully pot connected to manhole N3.

Figure 1. Diagram and photograph of the laboratory-scale physical model used in this study.

Experimental setup and procedure

The methodology considered three phases. (1) Characterization of the synthetic RDS load. (2) RDS flushing test on the physical model. (3) Analysis of the RDS load in the components of the road drainage system (road surface, gully pot and in the flow discharged into the manhole). Each of the phases considered are detailed below. (1) The RDS used in this study was dry vacuumed from an urban tunnel roadway (A Coruña, Spain; average daily traffic > 15000 vehicles/day), next to the curb (0.50 m). Afterwards, a plastic fibre brush was used to dislodge the RDS strongly adhered to the surface, which was also collected by dry vacuuming. The RDS particle size was determined using ISO 2591 methods (size fractions: < 63, 125, 250, 500, 1000, and 2000 μm) (ISO, 2007). The synthetic RDS used in this study was prepared by mixing the different size fractions to achieve realistic granulometry following literature measurements: < 63 = 9.90%, < 125 = 23.6%, < 250 = 41.6%, < 500 = 66.8%, < 1000 = 94.7% and < 2000 μm = 100%. The RDS was uniformly deposited on the road surface by means of a device consisting of three sieves in series, which were decreasing in pore size (6, 6 and 3 mm). In Figure 2, the RDS deposition area position is included (rectangular dimensions: width = 1 m and length = 2 m).

(2) Initially, a hydrological characterization of the physical model was performed at laboratory scale. This characterization allows accurate measurement of runoff flow, which, together with comprehensive topographic data and accurate intensity mapping, provides a crucial basis for the analysis of sediment transport processes. Two tests were performed for constant rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h and a duration of 10 minutes. Water depth at five points on the surface of sub-basin B2 and runoff flow at the outlet of gully pot 2 were determined using ultrasound sensors placed on the surface and over a triangular weir inside the gully. In addition, runoff velocities in two points were estimated by Large Scale Particle Image Velocimetry from recorded videos. Measurement points were included in Figure 2. After the hydrologic characterization, a series of wash-off tests were performed on the physical model considering RDS loads of 100, 150 and 200 g/m^2 and rain intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the previous hydrologic characterization tests and the RDS flushing tests. Deionized water was used in the latter tests.

(3) At the end of each test in the physical model, a mass balance was performed in relation to the total RDS load initially deposited on the road surface and that remaining on the surface, in the gully pot and in the flow discharged into the manhole. The remaining RDS on the road surface and in the gully pot was collected by wet vacuum. RDS collection in the manhole was performed as follows, for 31 bottles for each test: six bottles every 10 sec. (01:00), 13 bottles every 5 sec. (01:00 - 02:00), three bottles every 20 sec. (02:00 - 03:00), two bottles every 30 sec. (03:00 - 04:00), and seven bottles every min. (4:00 - 11:00). This allowed all surface runoff to be collected during the 10-minute duration of each trial plus an additional minute according to the time of concentration of the physical model road sub-basin. The particle size distribution of the remaining RDS on the road surface, in the gully pot and discharge end flow was determined using a laser diffractometer (Beckman Coulter LS 13 320, Aqueous Liquids Module) (ISO, 2007). The sample collection system in the inspection manhole made it possible to determine the pollutagrams (D. Li et al., 2023) in relation to the following water quality parameters: TUR, TSS, and electrical conductivity (EC).

Lastly, the following standards were considered to perform laboratory analyses of each of the parameters considered: TUR, Standard Method 2130 B; EC, Standard Method 2510 B; TSS, Standard Method 2540 D (Bridgewater et al., 2012).

Table 1. Characterization tests and simulation scenarios considered.

RDS Load [g/m ²]	Rainfall intensity [mm/h]	Water type	Duration [s]															
No RDS	30	Drinking water	600															
No RDS	50	Drinking water	600															
100	30	Deionized water	600															
100	50	Deionized water	600															
150	30	Deionized water	600															
150	50	Deionized water </tr <tr> <td>200</td> <td>30</td> <td>Deionized water</td> <td>600</td> </tr> <tr> <td>200</td> <td>50</td> <td>Deionized water</td> <td>600</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No RDS</td> <td>30</td> <td>Deionized water</td> <td>600</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No RDS</td> <td>50</td> <td>Deionized water</td> <td>600</td> </tr>	200	30	Deionized water	600	200	50	Deionized water	600	No RDS	30	Deionized water	600	No RDS	50	Deionized water	600
200	30	Deionized water	600															
200	50	Deionized water	600															
No RDS	30	Deionized water	600															
No RDS	50	Deionized water	600															

Results and discussion

Depths, flows and velocities were measured at the points marked in Figure 2 (left) for both rain intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h. Flow discharge results and an example of depths are included also in Figure 2 showing stationary flows up to 0.11 and 0.24 L/s and depths up to 4 and 6 mm in the curb area. In addition, elevation map and rain intensity maps in the study area complemented this hydraulic characterization to represent test conditions before analysing sediment transport processes.

Figure 2. Elevation map, measurement points and variables considered in the hydraulic characterization of the experiments (left). Examples of flow discharge at the gully pot (DS6) and water depth (DS3) time series are included (middle and right, respectively).

The results showed that under the lower rainfall intensity scenario (30 mm/h) RDS tended to remain more on the road surface (remaining load = 55.7%, D50 = 386 μ m, Figure 3). In the gully pot, a comparatively lower remaining RDS load (29.3%) and a higher D50 (483 μ m) were observed. The D50 in the gully pot (remaining load) was higher to the initial deposited (412 μ m) on the road surface before the start of the test (synthetic sediment). A lower remaining RDS load (6.70%) and a lower D50 (90 μ m) were observed in the discharge inside the manhole. The results showed that under the highest rainfall intensity scenario (50 mm/h) RDS tended to accumulate inside the gully pot (65.4% by mass) and with a finer grain size (D50 = 454 μ m, Figure 3). At the surface, a lower remaining RDS load (18.2%) and a similar D50 (338 μ m) were observed. At the downhole discharge, a higher remaining RDS load (14.3%) and an increase in D50 (95 μ m) were observed. Thus, the results hinted comparatively that the remaining RDS load in the gully pot and that discharged into the manhole were directly related to rainfall intensity. Indeed, the remaining RDS load on the road surface was inversely related to rainfall intensity.

Figure 3. Bar graph for remaining RDS load (upper) and grain size curves (down) for each component of the physical model.

Additionally, during the tests, a direct correlation was observed between TSS concentration and turbidity (minimum r -Pearson = 0.921), and between TDS concentration and EC (minimum r -Pearson = 0,992) in the discharge into the manhole. The results suggested that with increasing rainfall intensity the flushing of the RDS tended to be faster (Figure 4). In other words, the peak TSS concentration for the 50 mm/h rainfall intensity tended to occur first (1min:35s) compared to the peak TSS concentration for the 30 mm/h rainfall intensity (2min:20s). The faster formation of a water sheet, with higher draughts and velocities, possibly mobilized the RDS earlier. Indeed, the depletion of the available RDS load tended to be faster for the higher rainfall intensity scenario (50 mm/h). In this study, we also performed a complete analysis of mass fluxes, including by RDS particle size ranges, although these analyses are not shown in this synthetic communication.

Figure 4. Behavior of TSS concentration and turbidity over time (left), and TDS and EC concentration over time (right).

Conclusions and future work

The results suggest that during the design and management of road drainage systems it is relevant to consider the variation in rain intensity. This variation conditions the remaining RDS load on the road, in the gully pot and that discharged into the manhole. There is an inverse relationship between the rain intensity and the remaining RDS load on the road surface. There is a direct relationship between the rain intensity and the remaining load in the gully pot and that discharged into the manhole. Increasing precipitation intensity increases the magnitude of the concentration peak in the runoff discharged into the sewer manhole and this concentration peak tends to occur faster. This trend is more evident in TSS and turbidity compared to TDS and EC.

References

- Bridgewater, L., Association, A.P.H., Association, A.W.W., Federation, W.E., 2012. Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater. American Public Health Association.
- García-Haba, E., Naves, J., Hernández-Crespo, C., Goya-Heredia, A., Suárez, J., Anta, J., Andrés-Doménech, I., 2023. Influence of sediment characteristics on long-term hydrology and water quality behaviour during the clogging process of a permeable asphalt. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 53, 103658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2023.103658>
- Hu, L., Zhao, H., 2022. Influence of particle size on diffuse particulate pollutants in combined sewer systems. *Science of The Total Environment* 846, 157476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157476>
- ISO, 2007. ISO 2591-1:1988, Test sieving - Part 1: Methods using test sieves of woven wire cloth and perforated metal plate. American National Standards Institute, Geneva, Switzerland.
- ISO, 2007. ISO 13320-1:1999, Particle size analysis -- Laser diffraction methods -- Part 1: General principles.
- Li, D., Hou, J., Zhou, Q., Lyu, J., Pan, Z., Wang, T., Sun, X., Yu, G., Tang, J., 2023. Urban rainfall-runoff flooding response for development activities in new urbanized areas based on a novel distributed coupled model. *Urban Climate* 51, 101628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2023.101628>
- Li, L., Li, H., Zhao, H., 2023. Modeling the wash-off of road-deposited sediments with different particle-sizes on asphalt and concrete roads. *Journal of Hydrology* 625, 130115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.130115>
- Venghaus, D., Neupert, J.W., Barjenbruch, M., 2023. Evaluation of a Modular Filter Concept to Reduce Microplastics and Other Solids from Urban Stormwater Runoff. *Water* 15, 506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15030506>
- Wang, Q., Zhang, Q., Dzakpasu, M., Lian, B., Wu, Y., Wang, X.C., 2018. Development of an indicator for characterizing particle size distribution and quality of stormwater runoff. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 25, 7991–8001. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-1074-z>
- Yarmoshenko, I., Malinovsky, G., Baglaeva, E., Seleznev, A., 2020. A Landscape Study of Sediment Formation and Transport in the Urban Environment. *Atmosphere* 11, 1320. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11121320>